

POTTERY ARTIFACTS FROM THE 10TH–12TH CENTURIES OF TESHIKKOPRIKTEPA

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Annotation. *The article is based on the pottery collection from the archaeological site of Teshikkopriktepa, located in Tashkent, which was discovered and transferred to the State Museum of History of Uzbekistan in 1962. The collection, dating back to the 10th–12th centuries, is focused on ceramic vessels. The article describes different types of pottery, categorized into glazed and unglazed varieties. It explores how the vessels, such as the cauldron, were used for cooking, while the pot and jug were served for transporting and storing liquids, and the bowl and cup were utilized for distributing liquids and food.*

Key Words: *Tashkent, Teshikkopriktepa, pottery, cauldron, lid, pot, jug, bowl, cup, glaze, engobe.*

TESHIKKO‘PRIKTEPADAGI X-XII ASRLARGA OID KULOLCHILIK ASARLARI

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Аннотация. мақола Тошкент шаҳрида жойлашган Тешиккўприктепа археологик ёдгорлигидан топилиб, 1962 йилда Ўзбекистон тарихи давлат музейига топширилган 37-коллекциянинг 10–12-асрларга оид кулолчилик идишларига боғишланган. Унда кулолчилик буюмларининг сирланган ва сирланмаган турларига бўлиб тавсифланиб, мажмуадаги идишлардан қозонларнинг таомларни пиширишига, тувак ва кўзаларнинг суюқликларни ташишида ва сақлашида, коса ва пиёлаларнинг суюқлик ва таомларни тақсимлашида фойдаланганлиги хусусида фикр юритилган.

Калит сўзлар: Тошкент, Тешиккўприктепа, кулолчилик, қозон, қопқоқ, тувак, кўза, коса, пиёла, сир, ангоб.

КЕРАМИЧЕСКИЕ АРТЕФАКТЫ X–XII ВЕКОВ ИЗ ТЕШИККОПРИКТЕПА

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Аннотация: татъя посвящена керамическим сосудам X–XII веков из 37-й коллекции, которая была найдена на археологическом памятнике Тешиккуприктепа в городе Ташкенте и передана Государственному музею истории Узбекистана в 1962 году. В нем были представлены керамические изделия как глазурованного, так и неглазурованного типа, что отражало использование казанов в комплексе для приготовления блюд, горшков и кувшинов для транспортировки и хранения жидкостей, а также чаш (пиялушек) и плошек (касушек) для раздачи жидкостей, и блюд.

Ключевые слова: Ташкент, Тешиккоприктепа, керамика, казан (котёл), крышка, горшок, кувшин, чашка, чаша, глазурь, ангоб.

Introduction

In archaeological research, the pottery items found and collected due to various circumstances have a special place in addressing certain issues related to the economy and culture of the people who lived in different periods and regions. Specifically, the collection of pottery vessels found at Teshikkopriktepa can be considered part of these items.

Teshikkopriktepa is located in the city of Tashkent, Chilonzor district, along Bunyodkor Avenue (east), near the "Novza" metro station. The site is situated 444 meters above sea level and has an irregular rectangular shape. Currently, only the ark (fortified wall) of the monument remains, with a height of up to 6 meters. The length of the site is 35 meters, the width is 22 meters, and the total area is 1.57 hectares.

In the 1930s, regional historian Dmitry Bukinich (1882–1939) visited Teshikkopriktepa several times and collected archaeological artifacts. In 1947, V. I.

Sprishovsky conducted archaeological excavations at Teshikopriktepa [Филанович: 16]. However, the data obtained from these studies were not published. In the 1950s, staff members from the Department of Archaeology at Tashkent State University (now NUU) conducted archaeological observations. In 1962, archaeologists Konstantin Shakhurin and Yuri Buryakov (1934–2015) carried out research work at the site. In 1968, the Tashkent archaeological expedition, including members of the group led by Margarita Filanovich, conducted further investigations. The findings related to Teshikopriktepa and its study are briefly mentioned in the scientific works of Margarita Filanovich [Древний Ташкент: 11, 112; Древности Ташкента: 67, 116, 122; Филанович: 15–16, 181]. Research indicated that Teshikopriktepa dates back to the 5th–12th centuries, covering the period of the Turkic Khaganate, the Arab Caliphate invasions, the Tahirid rule under the caliphate, and the relatively independent Samanid and Karakhanid periods. The structure of the site was characterized by the division of the ark into separate rooms, surrounded by a thick outer wall, and constructed using raw brick and clay.

According to research, Teshikopriktepa was quite advanced during its time. The fortress, located in the central part, contained buildings from the 5th–8th centuries, which were destroyed during the Arab invasion in the 8th century and turned into ruins. Life was restored during the 9th–12th centuries in the ark and its surrounding area. The population engaged in ironworking and the production of metal goods. During this period, Teshikopriktepa was located on the caravan route leading from the south to the administrative center of Shash (Chach), the capital city of Binkat, making it a trade and handicraft hub. At the beginning of the 13th century, during the military campaigns led by Genghis Khan, the site was completely destroyed. After that, life at Teshikopriktepa did not recover.

Material and methods

In 1962, a total of 81 ceramic artifact samples found by Konstantin Shakhurin from Teshikkopriktepa and its surroundings were transferred to the State Museum of History of Uzbekistan. These artifacts are preserved in the museum's 37th collection. The collection includes 34 pottery items from the 10th–12th centuries, which were the focus of the research. Scientific analysis of these artifacts not only helps determine their period but also sheds light on the distinctive features of the pottery used in everyday life, such as their construction, decoration, and structure. These pottery items can be conditionally classified into two groups: glazed and unglazed clay vessels.

Unglazed Vessels.

In the collection, there are three types of unglazed vessels: 3 cauldrons, 2 lids, and 8 jugs. All of these were made using a pottery wheel and have the following characteristics:

Cauldrons. There are 3 fragments of cauldrons, which correspond to the rim and shoulder parts of the cauldrons. These cauldrons are made from clay mixed with crushed limestone, flint, sand (dresva), and chamotte. After firing, their color is light reddish-brown. The surface of the cauldrons is coated with a white-grayish glaze. They have scorch marks on the surface due to exposure to fire. The rims of the cauldrons are thickened outward. The diameters of their mouths, based on the fragments, are as follows: one has a mouth diameter of 28 cm, another 21 cm, and the third one is 20 cm. One of the cauldrons has a curved handle on its shoulder. According to the technique of making, construction, and glazing, similar cauldrons have been found at several archaeological sites in the Tashkent region, including Noghoikurgon (Kugaitepa), and they are dated to the 10th–12th centuries [Normurodov: II Annex, Figure 39, No. 3]. Judging by their similarities, such cauldrons are designed to sit well on a stove, allowing the flame to reach more of the body and cook the contents quickly and efficiently, and thus, they are typically made with a round or oval base. This provides a basis for dating the cauldrons found at Teshikkopriktepa to the same period.

The technique of making the 10th–12th-century cauldrons from Teshikkopriktepa ensured that they were heat- and fire-resistant. These cauldrons could have been used for cooking both thick and liquid foods, such as milk, boiled soups, and stews. Their natural composition also ensures that they do not negatively affect the taste of food. This is confirmed by the fact that today, in restaurants across different regions of Uzbekistan, a very tasty dish called “Kozha shorva” is prepared, which is made using similar clay vessels.

Lids. There are 2 fragments of lids in the collection, made from pure clay, shaped into discs and glazed in a cream color. One of the lids lacks the edges, and the surface has a handle resembling a mushroom shape at the center. The second fragment is one edge of a lid, decorated with a comb-like tool around the circumference near the edge. The underside of this lid shows traces of fine sand that likely adhered during the firing process to prevent the lid from sticking to the kiln. Similar lids have been found in archaeological excavations in the Tashkent region, and they are also dated to the 10th–12th centuries. These lids were widely used to cover containers to prevent the contents from spilling and also to seal cauldrons while cooking.

Jugs. There are 8 artifacts related to jugs in the collection, all made from pure clay using a pottery wheel. The marks left by the potter’s fingers while the wheel was spinning can be seen as wave-like patterns on the inside of the bowls. The walls of these jugs are about 0.5–0.9 cm thick, with mouth diameters ranging from 7.5 cm to 9–10 cm. Most of the jugs are glazed in cream) and reddish hues, with a few glazed in gray. The color of the glaze after firing is typically the same as the original glaze, such as the reddish-brown or gray shades. Some jugs are decorated with wave-like lines around their necks and shoulders, created through scraping. The bottom of one of these jugs shows a diameter of 4.5 cm, while others represent parts of the sides or necks. One group of these jugs has a handle placed in a "Г" shape on the lip or neck of the jug and its shoulder. These jugs have been compared with similar artifacts from the Tashkent

region, Fergana Valley, and the archaeological site of Akhsikent [Древности Ташкента: 76. – Fig. 33:1, 33:4, 33:6, 33:8, 33:9, 33:12; Буряков: – Fig. 10, 12; Анарбаев: 427 – 484; Normurodov D. Appendix II. Fig. 49:18]. Many of the elegant jugs found in urban areas, villas, and palaces likely contributed to the aesthetic decoration of dining tables. Additionally, the natural storage properties of these jugs helped preserve food products, especially in the heat of summer, keeping them cool.

Glazed Pottery.

The collection includes four types of glazed pottery: pots (2 pieces), a jug (1 piece), bowls (16 pieces), and a small vessel (1 piece). All of these items were crafted from fine clay using a potter’s wheel. The color of the clay after firing is typically a reddish-brown (brick color), with a white glaze applied over it. The glaze features geometric, epigraphic, and plant-like patterns in white, black, red, yellow, green, brown, and olive tones. These patterns are followed by a final transparent glossy or light yellowish glaze finish. The detailed description of each item is as follows:

Pots. There are 2 glazed bowls in the collection, both having wide openings. One of them is a turnip-shaped bowl with a single handle that connects the neck and shoulder of the vessel. The body diameter of this pot is approximately 12–13 cm. The decoration on the surface includes white and yellow circles with fine white lines inside them, creating a distinct pattern. The surface is finished with a glossy, transparent glaze. A similar bowl was found during an excavation in the Kokcha neighborhood of Tashkent, and it is dated to the 10th century [Ильцова: 69, No. 39].

The second pot is oval-shaped and features a neck and shoulder transition with a white glaze on the surface, overlaid with a dark brown brushstroke pattern. It is also finished with a transparent glossy glaze. Similar vessels have been found in other archaeological sites in the Tashkent region, and they are also dated to the 10th–12th centuries [Ильцова: 187, No. 116; 272, No. 237; 355, No. 314; 356, No. 315; 572–575]. These glazed jugs, compared to the unglazed ones mentioned earlier, are

considered more valuable. They were likely used by wealthier households, especially during guest receptions, which could explain their rarity.

Jug. The jug is a unique glazed artifact. Its neck and upper part are glazed in green, distinguishing it from the unglazed pots. The disc-shaped flat bottom of the jug has a diameter of 7 cm. One side has a handle, which originally had a loop connecting the shoulder to the neck, although the handle is now lost. Similar jugs have been found in multiple archaeological sites in the Tashkent region, dated to the 11th–12th centuries [Ильясова: 187, No. 116; 272, No. 237; 355, No. 314; 356, No. 315; 572–575]. This type of glazed jug was likely used in a variety of settings, similar to the glazed bowls.

Platter (Lagan). The platter is slightly tilted at the sides. It is decorated with black and reddish-brown patterns, with greenish stains applied to the interior. Based on the fragment, the diameter of the opening is 31 cm. Similar basins have been found in the Tashkent region, and their designs, structure, and decoration suggest they date back to the 10th–11th centuries [Ильясова: 598].

Bowls. The collection includes 16 bowls. These bowls are either conical or semi-spherical in shape. Most of them have a circular base (base diameter ranging from 9 cm to 10.7 cm) and a wide mouth with diameters ranging from 19 cm to 33 cm.

The decoration of these bowls includes motifs such as olive-colored plant (flower) designs, triangular patterns, dark brown circles with olive "Г" shapes, palm leaf-like designs, and flower-like designs that widen from the center to the mouth of the bowl in dark and reddish colors. Some bowls also feature Arabic inscriptions, such as the epigraphic decoration with the word “al-yumn (اليمن)”. These bowls, with their construction techniques, shape, and decoration, are similar to those found in archaeological sites in the Tashkent region, including from Binkat (Tashkent city), Banokat-Shahrukhia, and are dated to the 10th–11th centuries with palm-leaf decorations [Культура и искусство древнего Узбекистана: 182. № 715; Брусенко: 72–73. Table. 45:3; Ильясова: 93. № 63, 573. № 482; Normurodov: Fig. 49:18] and

Arabic inscriptions are specifically identified as being from the 10th century [Ильцова: 114, No. 109]. The bowls with spherical shapes and those with epigraphic decorations are dated to the 11th century [Филанович; Ильцова: 296-313, 507-512]. These bowls were primarily used to serve liquid dishes, but they also likely served an aesthetic function, enhancing the appearance of the table setting.

Cups. One fragment of a cup has been found, which is conical in shape, widening from bottom to top, with a ring-shaped raised base. The surface of the cup is decorated with olive-colored paint, featuring a floral design with red-colored paint in between the flowers. A "r"-shaped pattern and dot decorations in olive color are applied around the mouth and the lower part of the cup. Except for the bottom and near-bottom areas, the rest of the cup is coated with a light yellow, transparent glaze. The dimensions of the cup are as follows: height 4.4 cm, mouth diameter 13 cm, and base diameter 4 cm. Similar cups with comparable production techniques, structure, and decoration have been found in several archaeological sites in the Tashkent region, including Tashkent city and Banokat-Shahrukhia, dating to the 11th century [Брусенко: 72–73. 47. Table. 34: 9, 2; 39: 5; 40: 4, 3; Ильцова: 93. № 63, 364. № 323, 365. № 324]

Conclusion

The above details about the ceramic artifacts from Teshikkopriktepa provide insights into the pottery traditions of the 10th–12th centuries, particularly in the context of cooking, storing, transporting, and distributing liquids. The use of both glazed and unglazed pottery, along with their distinctive decorative features, reflects the aesthetic values of the time and offers a glimpse into the daily and ceremonial practices of the population. The diverse decorations on these items expand our understanding of the visual culture and artistic preferences of the people from that era.

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